

Tax Incentives and Financial Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Oyo State Nigeria

Ayotunde Kikelomo ONIGBINDE¹, Kolawole Fatai BISIRIYU² and Ayoola Abimbola ESO³

¹Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria, onigbindekike@gmail.com || +447867413353

²Assistant Director Tax, Large Taxpayer Audit Department, Federal Inland Revenue Service, Lagos, Nigeria, +2348033670220; bkolawole.kb@gmail.com; bisiriyu.kolawole@firs.gov.ng

³Department of Finance, Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Lagos, Nigeria ayoeso@hotmail.com; +234 802 291 3114

Abstract

The problems of high tax rates, multiple taxation, complex tax regulations and lack of proper enlightenment or education about tax related issues are of tremendous concern to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The above concern was prime centripetal to the study. Therefore, the study sought to establish the effect of tax holiday on financial performance of SMEs Holders. The study adopted cross-sectional survey design. The sample size was established with the use of the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. Three hundred and seventy-five (375) respondents were derived at. ANOVA analyses were used for the data analysis. The main theory that anchored this study is the Ability to pay theory. The result revealed that capital allowance tax influence financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. In addition, the result also revealed a significant relationship between corporate income tax and financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. The study recommends the adoption, by policy makers, of strategic incentive plans or targeted incentive scheme that targets specific industry or a strategic tax incentive that adds value or contributes positively to the economy.

Keywords: Capital allowance, Corporate income tax, Financial performance, Tax incentive, SMEs

Word Count: 183

Introduction

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have performed poorly in Nigeria, and in some cases have even collapsed, as a result of a variety of challenges confronting this critical sector of the Nigerian economy. Several of the obstacles identified in the body of literature as contributing to the problems include the following: deplorable infrastructure; insufficient managerial and entrepreneurial skills; financing difficulties; limited demand for their products and services; limited capacity for research and development as well as innovation; insufficient technology system; burden of multiple taxes; lack of a business plan or a good business plan; and recruitment of incompetent employees (Abdullahi, Jakada & Kabir, 2016).

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have been classified as an informal sector. This sector is said to represent the economic unit for which statistical data are difficult to obtain and thus are not fully captured by the state's tax net. Additionally, this sector is defined by low earnings, income instability, and a lack of access to basic protections and services (Aina, Aderibigbe, Adigun & Oyedokun, 2017). In Nigeria, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises are

said to account for 97 percent of productive units. Although they are smaller in size, they are the most important enterprises in the economy because their aggregated effects exceed those of larger companies.

Thus, tax incentives contribute to the recovery of capital expenditures, particularly those incurred during periods of poor performance. Tax incentives are intended to encourage and stimulate economic activity and investment by businesses and individuals. They are government-led fiscal policies aimed at revitalizing, rehabilitating, and stabilizing individuals, and corporate entities. The government also uses tax incentives to direct certain economic activities toward vital sectors of the economy where they are not felt or do not exist. Tax incentives will not only create jobs but will also encourage self-employed individuals to form limited liability companies (Philips, 2010). This will result in an increase in the firm's profitability. A healthy economy can be achieved by providing generous tax incentives to corporate taxpayers for projects whose profitability is unlikely to materialize for approximately three to five years.

Taxation has been defined as a charge or levy levied by a government on a semi-finished or finished product, income, or activity in order to fund infrastructure and engineer long-term economic growth and development. Taxation also functions as a means of wealth redistribution. Though it was asserted that "taxation has profound beneficial effects in fostering more accountable government," the Nigerian socio-political environment has rendered accountability in the public sector a wild goose chase due to the endemic corruption that continues to pervade the public service. While it was unambiguously established that the availability and collection of tax is a necessary condition for economic growth and development, it was also established that the sustainability, growth, and development of SMEs are also contingent on tax incentives, as this sector may be unable to compete favorably with large corporations (Olaniyi, Mustapha & Oyedokun, 2019).

To substantiate the importance of tax incentives on the financial performance of SMEs, it has been suggested that one of the viable fiscal policy tools for encouraging entrepreneurship/private business initiative, growth, and taxation is taxation and generous tax policies. Low tax rates without multiplicity and generous tax breaks for new businesses are said to stimulate private sector growth. Due to the critical role of SMEs in Nigeria's economy, the government felt compelled to offer incentives to sector operators. Unfortunately, the growth of these businesses is reported to be quite discouraging, as many fail to survive two (2) to three (3) years after establishment. It was observed that approximately 75% of SMEs in Nigeria perish during their infancy, failing to survive beyond their fourth anniversary. One of the major issues discovered is that multiple taxes imposed on SMEs are a significant factor in the abrupt closure of these businesses in Nigeria, as these illegal taxes continue to consume a sizable portion of their earnings (Oluboba, 2011).

While there is a widespread perception that taxes are an important source of revenue for economic development and the provision of social services, the difficulties encountered are in the area of the negative relationship between taxes and a business's ability to survive and expand. SMEs face a number of challenges, including insufficient capital, irregular power supply, a lack of focus, insufficient market research, inadequate technical and managerial skills, environmental impacts, and government regulations that affect how SMEs operate. Additionally, SMES face challenges such as high tax rates, multiple taxation, complex tax regulations, and a lack of adequate enlightenment or education regarding tax-related issues.

In Nigeria, particularly this taxation issue, which is eating away at a sizable portion of the revenues generated by these SMEs for growth, sustainability, and survival. These factors have contributed to an increase in the number of records indicating a shortage of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs).

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between corporate tax incentives and financial performance of SMEs in Oyo state. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between corporate income, tax incentive and financial performance of SMEs.
2. Access how excise tax and custom duties incentives affect the financial performance of SMEs.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were created to fully address the issues with the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between corporate tax and financial performance of SMEs.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between excise tax, custom duties, and the financial performance of SMEs.

Literature Review

Tax Incentives

Tax incentives are defined as any special tax provisions granted to qualified investment projects or businesses that provide a beneficial departure from the general tax code. The pioneer status is a tax incentive governed by the Industrial Development (Income Tax Relief) Act, Cap 17 Laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004. It provides certain businesses with a three-year tax holiday that is renewable for another two years. Nigeria's tax system allows registered businesses to change their name or operations, or even leave the country, after their pioneer status expires, increasing the risk of abuse. This, among other things, casts doubt on the effectiveness of these so-called tax incentives and the opportunity cost associated with them (Ndajiwo, 2018).

Taxation can contribute to development and welfare in three ways: it must generate sufficient funds to finance high-quality public services and social transfers, it must provide incentives for increased employment and the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources, and it must be able to reallocate income. However, in the case of SMEs, taxation must take their income and survival needs into account. It is prudent to allow them a sufficient profit to expand their businesses (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

The current research illuminates the operations and workings of capital allowance and corporate income tax incentives as they relate to the performance of SMEs. A capital allowance is a tax credit granted to a taxpayer on certain capital expenditures. Capital allowance is granted to the owner of an asset that is used entirely, exclusively, and reasonably for business purposes. Capital allowance is a type of tax relief available to anyone who incurs qualifying capital expenditure during a basis period on assets used in trade or business at the end of the basis period (Basseyy, 2013).

Capital allowances are granted in lieu of depreciation on tangible non-current assets. Except for Research and Development, other intangible non-current assets are not considered to qualify for capital allowance purposes. Capital allowance is defined as the allowance for depreciation granted on tangible non-current assets (Oyedele & Erikume, 2015). Capital expenditure is not an expense that can be deducted from profits. However, capital expenditure frequently results in the creation of non-current assets such as plants, machinery, and buildings that are primarily used for profit generation. As a result, it is reasonable to grant tax relief on these items on which expenditure has been incurred. This type of relief is provided by special allowances, commonly referred to as capital allowances (Kibiel, 2014).

The rate at which a fixed asset depreciates varies by business. For example, a business may choose to write off the cost of a plant after five years, whereas another business with a similar plant in a similar establishment and in the same neighborhood may choose to write-off after fifteen years. To address this issue, income tax laws disallow depreciation charges as deductions from taxable profit and instead provide for a series of regulated capital allowances. Thus, capital allowances are used in place of depreciation as allowable deductions when calculating a business's chargeable income (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016).

Corporate tax is a tax on businesses' profits. Theoretical economists generally oppose profit taxes on the grounds that they restrain enterprise by imposing a penalty for success while providing no compensation for failure. Corporate taxation is introduced to rein in the excess profits generated by the World Wars. Various rates of profits tax were levied in the UK between 1945 and 1965, possibly justified on the grounds that since the Government accepted responsibility for full employment, conditions favorable to profit earning have been provided by the Government. Occasionally, discrimination is made in favor of undistributed profits in order to encourage businesses to reinvest profits in their operations. In 1963, the United Kingdom introduced a Corporation Tax to replace profit and income taxes on businesses. Profits distributed to shareholders were taxed twice under this system, with the company paying Corporation Tax and the shareholders paying income tax (Harelimana, 2018).

Before 1937 Income Tax Ordinance No. 23, there was no provision for company profits tax in Nigeria, and all previous Ordinances lacked such a provision. In 1937, the ordinance was amended to conform to British standards, except that the Nigerian Ordinance did not include provisions for corporate taxation. The government introduced a tax of 2 shillings and 6 pence in the 1 on company profits for the first time in 1939, pursuant to Companies Income Tax Ordinance No.14 of 1939.

Corporate taxes are intended to raise revenue by taxing a business's economic profits. In practice, the tax base is defined as net accounting profits, which are defined as gross revenue fewer operating expenses and capital adjustments. Often, a single statutory rate is used, which is usually the best option, especially when administrative constraints exist. The statutory rate of corporation tax is frequently an inadequate indicator of the tax's effect on revenue or investment behavior.

Financial Performance

Measures of financial performance take a variety of forms. These measures differ from each other on several dimensions, and many issues concern the choice of which financial measures to employ (Nmehielle 2022). For example, measures may be absolute (profit/sales), return-based (profit/capital, profit/equity), internal (profit/sales), external (market value of the firm), a level for a single period (one year), mean or growth rate or variability (measures of central

tendency and dispersion). With the use of mean, deviation, or trend, they introduced firm survival as one of the indicators of the effect of tax incentives, which was considered to be a very important stimulus to industrial development. This is a simple and effective way of improving the commercial profitability of and cash flow from investments such that incentives are made available to companies within the exemption period.

Tax incentives help to increase the profit prospects of a new venture and enable a firm to recover its capital costs more quickly. Notwithstanding, the costs recovered would eventually lead to reduced risks of investment, a quick build-up of the firm's assets and capital for re-investment. Investment tax credit is earned when qualifying new buildings and equipment are purchased by a manufacturing firm. The credit could be used to off-set government tax in the future, thereby reducing the cost of capital and offsetting federal tax. This eventually impacts on the cash flow of the firm that is used to evaluate the growth potentials of any organization. Tax incentive is granted for the purpose of enhancing business performance of the companies (Nmehielle, 2022).

Theoretical Review

This theory is anchored on the Benefit theory of taxation. Tax incentives are emphasized by the benefit theory of taxation, which maintains that the taxes agents pay should reflect the benefit they receive from the state's mix of goods and services. The benefits theory of tax establishes the framework for local taxation (Scherf & Weinzierl, 2020). As a result, it proposes that taxes should be zero or low for entities and individuals that receive no benefits from the state and high for those that do. Government-led infrastructure development benefits businesses the most. According to the agency theory of tax incentives, tax incentives compensate for other government-created impediments to business, implying that tax is used to address fiscal as well as market failure (Twesige & Gasheja, 2019). Thus, the purpose of granting incentive packages under the tax system is to stimulate business growth in the country and thus contribute to the government's agenda of economic growth, national development, job creation, and improved general welfare.

According to the ability to pay theory, tax burdens should be proportionately distributed among taxpayers, with a heavier burden falling on those who are better able to bear it. Additionally, the ability to pay theory proposes that those with more should pay more, justifying a progressive tax system. From this vantage point, it is expected that medium enterprises will have a greater capacity for tax compliance than small enterprises, as medium enterprises are more financially secure in terms of profitability than small enterprises. Additionally, compliance is justified by the ability to pay, which means that firms with more resources are more likely to pay their taxes on time than those with limited resources. The European Commission, the World Bank, and the National Board for Small Scale Industries all use the operational definition of SMEs to indicate the financial strength of medium-sized enterprises over small-sized enterprises (Anim, Awotwe, Nyarku & Kusi, 2020).

The transaction cost theory establishes a rationale for the use of non-market organizational modes. According to the theory, firms reduce transaction costs as a result of their effect on incentives, monitoring, and production structure. Costs associated with coordination, such as information processing required coordinating the work of tax authorities and SMEs, are more likely to favor medium-sized businesses than small businesses. According to this analogy, small businesses that are financially weak in comparison to medium-sized businesses may as well be unwilling to grow as much as medium-sized businesses, as taxes paid by such firms may

weaken their production capability, thereby reducing their growth potential (Dagdeviren & Robertson, 2016).

Empirical Review

Mumbua and Nekesa (2023) investigated effect of tax incentives on financial performance among manufacturing firms in Kenya with a case of Industrial Area, Nairobi) Tax incentive is a strategy employed by governments world over to attract investments in varied sectors of their economies. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of tax incentives on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya, taking manufacturing firms in Nairobi industrial area as a case study for 10 years. The study was guided by the following specific objectives: to find out how capital allowance affect financial performance of manufacturing companies in Kenya, to establish the effect of allowable deductions on financial performance of manufacturing companies in Kenya and to investigate effects of investment deductions on financial performance of manufacturing companies in Kenya. The study adopted deterrent theory, ability to pay theory, and agency theory. The study employed a descriptive research design, using stratified sampling methods. The study's target population was manufacturing companies in Kenya specifically in the Nairobi Industrial Area across all the categories as listed by the Kenya Association of Manufacturers directory as of 2022. The study collected secondary quantitative data which was analyzed using descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) and inferential statistics (correlation analysis) to determine the relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Tables and figures were used to present the analysis output. The findings indicated that tax incentives had a significant positive effect on financial performance, as they reduced the cost of capital for manufacturing firms, promoted innovation and competition, and led to increased productivity and efficiency. Based on these findings, the study recommended that the Kenyan government should continue to provide tax incentives to manufacturing firms and tailor them to the specific needs of each firm, while also encouraging innovation and competition in the sector through support for research and development, technology transfer, and training programs. Manufacturing firms are also encouraged to take advantage of the tax incentives to invest in capital-intensive projects and acquire capital assets. However, there is a need to review the current tax laws to make the tax incentives more flexible and attractive to potential investors, and to consider increasing the amount of tax incentives to further reduce the cost of capital for manufacturing companies.

Oyedokun and Taiwo (2022) examined the effect of tax incentives on financial performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria. The study adopted a longitudinal research design with the use of the data obtained from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The population of this study is all small and medium enterprises in Nigeria with a representative sample size of 41.5million. This study will use secondary data. The data was obtained from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria and reports of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) for the period between 1985 and 2020 for analysis. The study will use the ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique of analysis using time series data. The findings revealed that Capital Allowance Incentives and Pioneer Status Incentives have positive and significant effects on the financial performance of SMEs in Nigeria. The study, therefore, concluded that the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria is driven by Valued Added Tax, Customs and Excise Duties, and Other various taxes by state. In view of the foregoing, the study recommended that Government should create incentives as an encouragement to reduce tax evasion actions by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and

other incentives like Pioneer Status, Reduced company income tax, Loss Relief, etc., should be increased in other to encourage investors and enhance the growth of SMEs in the national economic growth.

Nmehielle (2022) assessed tax incentive practices and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Tax incentives are granted to enhance positive financial performance and growth of companies across various industries in the country. It is also encouraging to know that consumer goods companies are ranked as one of the pioneer companies. There is however some air of uncertainty as to the value or rationale behind the continued provision of tax incentives. The study examined the relationship between tax incentive practices and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objective was to investigate the relationship between annual allowance and return on assets. Secondary data was obtained from the annual reports of consumer goods firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NEG) Fact book on a time series of 2011-2020. Convenience sampling technique was adopted where 5 listed consumer goods were selected. Data sourced were subjected to a battery of robustness test, while Pearson's Product Moment (PPMC), Partial Correlation and Regression analysis used for data analysis and testing the hypothesis formulated. The study result indicated that there is a significant relationship between Annual Allowance and Return of Assets of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. The study recommended that the authorities responsible for administration of tax incentives should prioritize the process of granting tax incentives by making it easier for companies in the consumer goods have unrestrained access to tax incentives, so as to bolster productivity in the sector in order to promote made in Nigeria goods.

Omesi and Ine-Tonbarap (2022) investigated tax incentives and financial performance of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The research adopted ex-post facto design. The population for this study was twenty-one (21) listed consumer goods companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange and a sample size of twenty listed consumer goods companies. The instrument of the study was secondary data obtained from the company's published financial report or statements within the period of eleven (11) years, ranging from 2009-2019. The formulated research questions were analyzed with descriptive statistics. The hypotheses were tested at a significance level of .05 using the multiple regression analysis with the aid of E-view (10). The results of the findings were that there is positive and significant relationship between investment allowance and return on assets of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. On the other hand, there is positive and significant relationship between annual allowance and return on assets of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria and there is significant influence of share capital in the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study recommends among others that; to continually maintain high return on assets of consumer goods manufacturing industry and foster economic development. Captains of the industries and government should encourage investment by formulating and enacting laws that increase the rate of investment allowance from 15% to 20% on plants and machineries used in manufacturing business. No doubt manufacturing companies are benefiting financially from annual allowances. Also, the tax authority should consider proportionately increase of annual allowances if the period for a year of assessment happens to be a period of more than one year. This will attract more investors, thereby improving the economic growth of the country.

Mwangi (2021) assessed tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. Tax incentives have been an issue of great concern the world over as many governments

have applied the incentives to attract multinational companies as well as to promote the domestic manufacturing industries. Manufacturing sector in Kenya has continued to show significant drop in its contribution to the gross domestic product for the past 15 years. Therefore, the government introduced tax incentives as one of the measures to address the challenges of the growth of the sector. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The specific objectives of the study were to establish the effect of value added tax incentives, corporation tax incentives, custom duty incentives and double taxation treaty incentives on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study also determined the moderating effect of tax administration procedures on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Kenya. The study will be of great value to the government of Kenya in setting up policies on tax incentives. The study was anchored on tax discrimination theory, Laffer curve theory and agglomeration economies theory. Descriptive survey research design was adopted where a sample of 211 firms was selected by use of Yamane formula, from a target population of 447 manufacturing firms using stratified random sampling technique. The study relied on both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected using questionnaires while secondary data was collected over a period of 10 years covering 2009 to 2018. The targeted respondents were the accountants, auditors, and finance officers in the organizations. The response rate was 73.5%. Both descriptive and inferential data analysis was carried out such as ordinal regression model. Data was tested for multi-collinearity which was proved not to exist. The data was also tested for autocorrelation by use of Durbin Watson test and the data had no autocorrelation. Test of heteroscedasticity was carried out and the data confirmed not to suffer from heteroscedasticity. The study also tested the data for normality, the data violated the assumptions of normality. Data on dependent variables was transformed to ordinal scale by use SPSS. Due to violation of the assumption of normality the study adopted the ordinal regression analysis which is a non-parametric method of analysis. The findings of the study revealed that tax incentives had statistically significant influence on financial performance of manufacturing companies in Kenya. The findings also revealed that tax administration procedures which was the moderating variable had an antagonistic effect on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies. The study concluded that influences of VAT incentives, income tax incentives, custom duty incentives and double taxation treaty incentives leads to improvement in financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study therefore recommended that the management of manufacturing companies should utilize VAT incentives, income tax incentives, custom duty incentives and double taxation treaty incentives that are offered by the government. The study recommends that the government should review tax incentive policy so as to be able to widen the scope of tax incentives.

Twesige and Gasheja (2019) analyzed the effect of tax incentive on the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Rwanda taking SMEs in Nyarugenge as a case study. Qualitative and quantitative research approach was adopted. The population includes 49000 SMEs from agricultural, industrial, services and tourism sectors operating in Nyarugenge district. A sample of 136 SMEs was determined using Silovin and Yemen's formula of sample size. Simple random and purposive sampling techniques were used to select the sample. The data set was analysed using descriptive statistics. A multiple regression analysis was used to explain the relation between variables. The results from the study revealed that 75.7% of the respondents agreed that they know the tax laws, 78.7% agreed that they know the tax incentives that are available to SMEs. The results further revealed that wear and tear, loss carried forward and value-added tax (VAT) refund as the most tax incentives available to Rwandan SMEs as

evidenced by 100, 94.1 and 95.6%, respectively. The study indicated that there was a strong positive and significant relationship between tax incentives and the growth of small and medium enterprises in Rwanda as approved by coefficients of correlation equal to 88.8% of R-square. This meant that only 11.2% of the variation in the growth of SMEs was outside the tested variables. The study concluded that tax incentives are the key to the sustainable growth of SMEs. The government should design policies that specifically address issues related to the sustainable growth of SMEs.

Muada & Saidu (2019) examined the effect of tax incentives on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study used data collected from published annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies, and tax related submission from the investment promotion commission and Federal Inland Revenue Services. The study covered only seven (7) companies out of twenty-one (21) listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria which were published with available data for the period of eighteen (18) years (2000-2017). The study used parson's correlation and multiple regressions to establish the influence of tax incentive on financial performance of the sampled firms. The study found that capital allowance and loss relief had positive and significant influence on the performance of the sampled firms while investment allowance had positive but insignificant influence on the financial performance of the sampled firms. The study recommends that companies should take more advantage of tax incentives available to them, especially, the incentives related to investments that will help in straightening the productivity of the firms. While tax authorities should consider means of introducing more incentives for investors to critical sectors like consumer goods that have a direct relationship with agricultural output and country export. Tax authorities should also provide an easy enlightenment mechanism on the importance and advantages of tax incentives, especially the rural investment allowance that is geared towards increase in the provision of social amenities to rural areas among others.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The design was considered appropriate for this study as it assisted in an in-depth investigation to examine tax incentives and their influence on financial performance in selected firms. The total population of SMEs in Oyo state as at the last SMEDAN report was 6,131. Small Enterprises are 6,039 while medium enterprises were 92. The study population was all the registered small and medium enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo state as obtained from National Bureau of Statistics. The sample size was established with the use of the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula as such, 375 sample size was arrived at using the formula. Proportionately, small enterprise has a sample size of 369, while the medium enterprises was 6. Questionnaire was used to collect the data of the study and was analysed with ANOVA, and multiple regression analysis.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Data of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	152	40.5
	Female	223	59.5
	Total	375	100
Form of Business	Sole Proprietorship	123	32.8
	Private Limited Company	99	26.4
	Partnership	83	22.1

	Joint Venture	70	18.7
	Total	375	100
Position in Business	Owner	124	33.1
	Chief Accountant	66	17.6
	Manager	111	29.6
	Finance Manager	74	19.7
	Total	375	100
Highest Educational Qualification	Primary School Cert	27	7.2
	O'level Certificate	80	21.3
	First Degree	77	20.5
	Master's degree	104	27.7
	Higher Degree	87	23.2
	Total	375	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 above shows the classification of respondents according to gender, form of business, [position in business and their highest educational qualification. It shows distinction between male and female, 59.5% of the respondents are Females, while 40.5% of them were Males. This revealed that majority of the study respondents were females. The table also revealed the form of Business of the sampled respondents, 32.8% of the respondents were sole proprietorship, 26.4% were private limited company, 22.1% are partnership and 18.7% were joint venture. Thus, sole proprietorships were the highest respondents of the study. The table and figure 4.1.4 showed the position in business of respondents. The survey revealed that 33.1% of the respondents were the business owner, 29.6% of respondents were manager, 19.7% of them were finance manager while 17.6% of them are Chief accountant. Hence, business owners were the highest respondents of the study. The table also showed the highest educational qualification of the respondents. From the information gathered 7.2% of the qualifications were primary school certificate holders, 21.3% were secondary school certificate holders, 20.5% were first degree holders, 27.7% of the respondents were holders of master's degree while higher degree holders were 23.2%. Therefore, first degree holders were the major respondents of the study.

Table 2: Effect of Corporate Income Tax Incentive

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.
Our firm benefit from corporate income tax	227 (60.5%)	139 (37.1%)	3 (0.8%)	3 (0.8%)	3 (0.8%)	4.56	.639
Corporate income tax incentives promote firm expansion	195 (52.0%)	123 (32.8%)	19 (5.1%)	19 (5.1%)	19 (5.1%)	4.22	1.089

Corporate income tax incentives enhance firms' revenue	197 (52.5%)	173 (46.1%)	1 (0.3%)	1 (0.3%)	3 (0.8%)	4.49	.607
Total	206 (54.9)	145 (38.7)	8 (2.1)	8 (2.1)	8 (2.1)		
N=375, Weighed Average mean =4.42, Grand mean=3.29						4.42	0.778

Sources: 2024 **Researcher's** **field-report,**

Findings show that 60.5%, 37.1%, 0.8% respondents representing 98.4% agreed that their firm benefit from corporate income tax while 1.6% disagreed. The study also revealed that 52.0%, 32.8%, 5.1% of the respondents representing 89.9% agreed that corporate income tax incentives promote firm expansion while 10.1% feel otherwise, in additional, 52.5%, 46.1%, 0.3% respondents representing 98.9% agreed that corporate income tax incentives enhance firms' revenue while 1.1% disagreed.

Table 3: Summary of Effect of Corporate Income Tax Incentive

LEVEL	Category of scores	Responses	
		Frequency	Percentage
High	Above 70%	359	80.8
Moderate	30%-70%	8	2.1
Low	Below 30%	16	4.2
Total		375	100.0
Mean		4.42	
Standard Dev.		0.778	

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

The results of the findings show that majority of the respondents agreed that there was effect of corporate income tax incentive on financial performance of SMES holders. The mean and standard deviation used corroborate this claim. This was shown with the weighted average mean and standard deviation score of (**Weighed Average mean =4.42, Grand mean = 3.39**), The report reveals that there was employee engagement influence on financial performance of SMES holders.

Table 3: Effect of Exercise Tax Incentive

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.
Our firm benefit from exercise tax incentives	212 (56.5%)	150 (40.0%)	5 (1.3%)	5 (1.3%)	3 (.8%)	4.50	.674

Excise tax incentives promote financial performance	204 (54.4%)	124 (33.1%)	17 (4.5%)	15 (4.0%)	15 (4.0%)	4.30	1.011
Excise tax incentives encourage continuous operation of firms	203 (54.1%)	145 (38.7%)	9 (2.4%)	9 (2.4%)	9 (2.4%)	4.40	.849
Total	206 (54.9)	140 (37.3)	10 (2.7)	10 (2.7)	9 (2.4)		
N=375, Weighed Average mean =4.40, Grand mean=3.29						4.40	0.844

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Findings showed that 56.5%, 40.0% 1.3% respondents representing 97.8% agreed that their firm benefit from exercise tax incentives while 2.2% disagreed. The study also revealed that 54.4%, 33.1%, 4.5% respondents representing 92.0% agree that excise tax incentives promote financial performance while 8.0% disagreed. In addition, 54.1%, 38.7%, 2.4% respondents representing 95.6% agreed that excise tax incentives encourage continuous operation of firms while 4.4% disagreed.

Table 4: Summary of Exercise Tax Incentive

LEVEL	Category of scores	Responses	
		Frequency	Percentage
High	Above 70%	346	92.2
Moderate	30%-70%	10	2.7
Low	Below 30%	19	5.1
Total		375	100.0
Mean		4.40	
Standard Dev.		0.844	

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

The results of the findings showed that majority of the respondents agreed that there was effect of exercise tax incentive on financial performance of SMES holders. The mean and standard deviation used corroborate this claim. This was shown with the weighted average mean and standard deviation score of (**Weighed Average mean =4.40, Grand mean = 3.39**). The report revealed that there was an effect of exercise tax incentive on financial performance of SMES holders.

Table 5: Effect of Custom Duty Incentive

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std. Dev
Our firm benefits from customer duty incentives	198 (52.8%)	159 (42.4%)	6 (1.6%)	6 (1.6%)	6 (1.6%)	4.43	.753
Custom duty incentives promote firm's operation	197 (52.5%)	142 (37.9%)	12 (3.2%)	12 (3.2%)	12 (3.2%)	4.33	.930
Custom duty incentive promote SMEs set-up	219 (58.4%)	114 (30.4%)	14 (3.7%)	14 (3.7%)	14 (3.7%)	4.36	.990
Total	205 (54.7)	138 (36.8)	11 (2.9)	11 (2.9)	11 (2.9)		
N=375, Weighed Average mean =4.37, Grand mean=3.29						4.37	0.891

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Findings showed that 52.8%, 42.4%, 1.6% respondents representing 96.8% agreed that their firm benefits from customer duty incentives while 3.2% disagreed. The study also revealed that 52.5%, 37.9%, 3.2% of the respondents representing 93.6% agreed that custom duty incentives promote firm's operation while 6.4% feel otherwise, in addition, 58.4%, 30.4%, 3.7% respondents representing 86.2% agree that Custom duty incentive promote SMEs set-up while 13.8% disagreed.

Table 6: Summary of Effect of Custom Duty Incentive

LEVEL	Category of scores	Responses	
		Frequency	Percentage
High	Above 70%	345	80.8
Moderate	30%-70%	54	12.6
Low	Below 30%	28	6.6
Total		427	100.0
Mean		4.01	
Standard Dev.		1.257	

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

The results of findings show that majority of the respondents agreed that there was effect of custom duty incentive on financial performance of SMES holders. The mean and standard deviation used corroborate this claim. This was shown with the weighted average mean and standard deviation score of (**Weighed Average mean =4.01, Grand mean = 3.39**), The report

reveals that there was effect of custom duty incentive on financial performance of SMES holders

Analysis of Research Questions

RQ1: What is the relative between corporate income, tax incentive and financial performance of SMEs?

Table 7: Summary of multiple regressions of corporate income, tax incentive and financial performance of SMEs

R=.453						
R²=.521						
Adj. R²=.584						
Std. Error = 9.646						
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (<i>p</i> value)	Remark
Regression	23.230	2	11.615			
Residual	1077.746	372	2.897	4.009	.019	Sig.
Total	1100.976	374				

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

As indicated in table 7, it was found that corporate income, tax incentive has combined significant relatives on financial performance of SMEs was significant ($F_{(2,372)} = 4.009$, $p < 0.05$). The result yielded a coefficient of multiple regression of $R = 0.453$ and multiple R-square of 0.521. The result also revealed that Adjusted $R^2 = 0.584$; indicating that about 58.4% of variance was accounted for by the independent variables. This implied that corporate income and tax incentive has significant influence on financial performance of SMEs.

Table 8: Summary Relatives of corporate income, tax incentive on financial performance of SMEs

Variable	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardize d coefficients	T	Sig. (<i>p</i> value)	Remark
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)			
(Constant)	10.521	.999	-	10.533	.000	
Corporate income	.057	.060	.083	1.936	.035	Sig.
Tax Incentives	.136	.053	.132	2.561	.011	Sig.

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Table 8 showed the unstandardized regression weight (β), the standardized error of estimate ($SE\beta$), the standardized coefficient, the t-ratio and the level at which the t-ratio are significant. As indicated in the table, Tax incentives ($\beta = 0.132$, $t = 2.561$, $p < 0.05$) was tested significant on financial performance of SMEs follow by corporate income ($\beta = 0.083$, $t = 2.542$, $p < 0.05$), were

independently significant. This implied that, corporate income and tax incentive had independently significant influence on financial performance of SMEs.

RQ2: How does excise tax and custom duties incentives relates to the financial performance of SMEs?

Table 9: Summary of multiple regression of excise tax and custom duties incentives and financial performance of SMEs

R=.463						
R²=.499						
Adj. R²=.518						
Std. Error = 1.711						
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (<i>p</i> value)	Remark
Regression	11.559	2	15.779			
Residual	1089.417	372	2.929	3.009	.014	Sig.
Total	1100.976	374				

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

As indicated in table 9, it was found that excise tax and custom duties incentives have combined significant influence on financial performance of SMEs ($F_{(2,372)}=3.009, p<0.05$). The result yielded a coefficient of multiple regression of $R=0.463$ and multiple R-square of 0.499. The result also revealed that Adjusted $R^2=0.518$; indicating that about 51.8% of variance was accounted for by the independent variables. This implied that excise tax and custom duties incentives have significant influence on financial performance of SMEs.

Table 10: Summary Relatives of excise tax and custom duties incentives on financial performance of SMEs

Variable	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig. (<i>p</i> value)	Remark
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)			
(Constant)	12.623	.847	-	14.909	.000	
Exercise tax	.107	.065	.924	2.866	.001	Sig.
Custom duties incentives	.078	.047	.720	2.065	.017	Sig.

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Table 10 showed the unstandardized regression weight (β), the standardized error of estimate ($SE\beta$), the standardized coefficient, the t-ratio and the level at which the t-ratio are significant. As indicated in the table, Exercise tax ($\beta=0.924, t= 2.866, p<0.05$) was tested significant on financial performance of SMEs follow by Custom duties incentives ($\beta=.720, t= 2.065, p<0.05$), were independently significant. This implied that, excise tax and custom duties incentives had independently significant influence on financial performance of SMEs.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H₁: There is no significant relationship between corporate tax and financial performance of SMEs.

Table 11: Result of PPMC showing the significant relationship between Corporate Income tax and financial performance of SMEs Holders

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Corporate Income tax	11.27	2.46	375	.620**	.000	Sig.
Financial performance	13.08	1.715				

*Sig. at .05 level

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Table 11 above shows that there was a positive significant relationship between Corporate Income tax and financial performance ($r = .620^{**}$, $N = 375$, $p < .05$) of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. The result rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between Corporate Income tax and financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State.

Hypothesis Two

H₂: There is no significant relationship between excise tax, custom duties, and the financial performance of SMEs.

Table 12: Result of PPMC showing the significant relationship between excise tax, custom duties and financial performance of SMEs Holders

Correlations		Financial Performance	Excise Duty	Custom Duty
Financial Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.057	-.057
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.269	.274
	N	375	375	375
Excise Duty	Pearson Correlation	.057	1	.382**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.269		.000
	N	375	375	375

Custom Duty	Pearson Correlation	-.057	.382**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.274	.000	
	N	375	375	375
	Mean	13.01	13.20	13.13
	Std. Deviation	1.716	1.482	2.018

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Sources: Researcher's field-report, 2024

Table 12 above shows that there was no significant relationship between Exercise Duty and financial performance ($r = .057$, $N = 375$, $p > .05$) the result show there was significant relationship between Custom Duty and financial performance ($r = .382$, $N = 375$, $p > .05$) of SMEs Holders in Oyo State The result accepted the null hypothesis and rejected the alternate hypothesis which states there is no significant relationship between Exercise and Duty custom on financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between corporate income tax and financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. A study conducted in Kenya corroborates the findings of the present study. The study found shows a positive correlation between tax incentives and financial performance for manufacturing companies in Kenya (Mumbua & Nekesa, s).

Hypothesis two accepted the null hypothesis and rejected the alternate hypothesis which states there is no significant relationship between Excise tax, custom duty and financial performance of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. The study supports the findings of a study carried out on the economic impact of high excise duties and/or the changes in excise duty implemented by national governments (Advocate, 2014)

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examines the relationship between corporate tax incentives and financial performance of SMEs in Oyo state. This research work clearly confirms that tax incentives are germane to the growth, development, and continued sustenance of small and medium enterprises. However, most of the tax incentives that are available in the tax law are not enjoyed by SMEs. It is only the large taxpayers that enjoy most of the tax incentives. Tax incentives play a vital role in ensuring that small and medium enterprises thrive because the government has made available tax holidays for pioneer companies, and the government also grants a few general and industry specific incentives. The study revealed that there is significant impact of corporate income tax on financial performance of selected SMEs in Oyo State.

This study offers the following recommendation:

1. Building SMEs capacity through the localization of supply chains requires the leadership from the top. And that SMEs should have adequate knowledge of the various tax incentives available to them so as to be able to make use of it.
2. The study noted the need for greater diversification in the incentives granted and greater sustainability. The study recommended the need for reducing the variability in the number of incentives among the firms so as to ensure the survival of a greater number of firms.

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